

Flexible Demand and Its Impacts on Future Utility-Scale Photovoltaic Integration and Generation Costs: Case Study on the Italian Energy Transition

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The energy transition implies an increase in electrical demand, which shall be met primarily by renewable energy sources, potentially raising costs for the system and the community. However, increasing consumption flexibility has the potential to reduce these additional costs by minimizing the risk of curtailment and reducing the need for new storage and grid line capacity. Few studies have been conducted to examine the techno-economic implications of improving consumption flexibility from an energy system perspective, but none have determined how these gains may affect future solar power integration costs. In this study, it is aimed to fill the gap by assessing the economic effects of flexible demand on solar integration and generation costs. Different scenarios for 2030 and 2040 of the Italian energy system are investigated taking into account future flexible demand availability and geographical distribution. In the results, it is shown that enabling a 12 h flexible demand can lower powerline transport capacity by up to 14%, and storage capacity by up to 25% in the 2040 scenarios. This corresponds to a reduction in photovoltaic (PV) generation costs from 11 to 13% by lowering overall PV integration costs, with peaks of up to 20% in some cases.

Plan (COM/2023/757)^[1] in November 2023 in accordance with the Green Deal objectives,^[2] which outlines a series of steps to strengthen cross-border and local European electrical networks, making them more flexible and digitalized. Because of the planned electrification of the building and transportation sectors, the EU Commission estimates that cross-border transmission capacity would double by 2030, requiring an investment of \approx €584 billion.

However, to avoid the costs of the energy transition being absorbed by end users through their electricity bills, they shall be redistributed within the energy sector. For example, the authors in refs. [3,4] redefined the levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) concept by including the costs of PV integration directly in the generation costs. These integration costs include the impacts of the PV production on both the grid infra-

structure and the existing power plants as well as the risk of curtailment. When they are included in the production costs, the authors in ref. [5] estimated that the PV production costs will rise by around 25%.

Improving consumption flexibility has the potential to reduce these additional costs by lowering the risk of curtailment and investment in new storage and grid line capacity, while also accelerating the system's decarbonization. Few studies have been conducted to analyze the techno-economic implications of increasing consumption flexibility from an energy system perspective.

The authors in refs. [6,7] used the BALMOREL model to calculate the impact of flexible demand on various national energy systems. The findings in ref. [6] demonstrated that the flexible demand reduces the electricity prices for consumers and the risk of curtailment for the PV and wind power plants, which saw revenues increase by 5 and 2%, respectively. Whereas, the revenues from flexible demand changes in ref. [7] depending on techno-economic parameters and the price volatility in the various analyzed market areas, even though it may contribute to peak shaving of up to 18.6% of total peak load in 2050. The REMix energy system model was used by the authors in ref. [8] to investigate the influence of demand response (DR) on the future German energy mix, which includes 70% variable renewable energy. The results show that DR replaces around 5 GW of peak power generation capacity and lowers the annual power supply costs between €230 and €580 billion. The ELTRAMOD electricity

1. Introduction

Photovoltaic (PV) technology is expected to play an important role in the upcoming sustainable energy transition. However, to sustain the ongoing increase in PV generation, grid infrastructures at all levels (both distribution and transmission) must be expanded and renovated, and storage capacity must be enhanced. For example, the European (EU) Commission published the Grid Action

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market model was used instead by the authors in ref. [9] to assess the DR potential for renewable energy sources (RES) integration in Germany, highlighting that the RES curtailment was reduced and the short-term fluctuations of the residual load were balanced. The economic potential of load shifting in various European day-ahead spot markets was studied in ref. [10], estimating a median potential profit of €12.4 MWh⁻¹. The market price spread and available power for load reduction and increase have the greatest influence on achievable benefits. The authors in ref. [11] showed that the flexible demand can lower power system operating costs, traditional generator cycling requirements, and the peak demand, while increasing RES usage in the Australian National Electricity Market. Finally, the authors in ref. [12] assessed the impacts of the flexibility on the consumption side for the future evolution of the Italian energy system, finding that flexible demand implementation could reduce the battery energy system storages (BESS) capacity by 2–6% and powerline transport capacity by 2–10%, resulting in energy system costs savings ranging from €758 to €8611 million.

It is evident that the studies cited earlier fail to evaluate the economic benefits from the perspective of PV production, particularly in determining the potential for reducing PV integration costs. This study aims to address this gap by assessing the economic impacts of flexible demand on the final PV generation costs, building on the preliminary analysis presented in ref. [12]. This research will estimate the economic impact of flexible demand on the integration and competitiveness of a specific power production technology by incorporating these economic

benefits into the calculation of production costs. Different scenarios are studied to assess the effects of flexible demand geographical distribution, comparing the situation of flexible load distributed based on baseload against flexible load distributed based on variable renewable energy sources (VRES) Macro regio availability.

Section 2 details the methodology and scenarios used to test this approach, while Section 3 presents the results. Finally, the conclusions are drawn in Section 4.

2. Experimental Section

2.1. PV Integration and Generation Costs

The methodology used in this study reviews and combines the PV generation cost calculation method from ref. [4] with the flexible demand assessment method from ref. [12]. The former aimed to establish a calculation method for the integration and generation costs of utility-scale PV plants. The latter evaluated the energy transition of a national energy system toward an RES-based system, incorporating various flexibility options, i.e., pumped hydro storages, BESS, and flexible demand.

According to ref. [4], the PV generation costs could be calculated using the system LCOE, where the traditional LCOE concept was extended to include integration costs, which was applied in this study according to Equation (1).

$$\text{sysLCOE} = \frac{\text{Inv} * \text{PV}_{\text{inst}} + \sum_{t=1}^N \frac{\text{Inv} * \text{PV}_{\text{opex}} * \text{PV}_{\text{inst}}}{(1+r)^t} + \sum_{t=1}^N \frac{(\text{Tr}_{\text{pv}} + \text{Bal}_{\text{pv}} + \text{Ad}_{\text{pv}} + \text{Dis}_{\text{pv}} + \text{Sto}_{\text{pv}}) * \text{PV}_{\text{prod}}}{(1+r)^t}}{\sum_{t=1}^N \frac{\text{PV}_{\text{prod}} * (1 - \text{curt}) * (1 - \text{deg})^t}{(1+r)^t}} \quad (1)$$

where Inv indicates the PV investment costs in € MW⁻¹, PV_{inst} indicates the PV-installed capacity in MW, PV_{opex} indicates the annual operational expenses expressed as a percentage of the PV investment, Tr_{pv} indicates the reinforcing transmission network costs in € MWh⁻¹, Bal_{pv} indicates the balancing costs in € MWh⁻¹, Ad_{pv} indicates the adequacy costs in € MWh⁻¹, Dis_{pv} indicates the reinforcing distribution network costs in € MWh⁻¹, Sto_{pv} indicates the storage costs in € MWh⁻¹, PV_{prod} indicates the annual PV production in MWh; curt indicates the PV curtailment expressed as a percentage, deg indicates the annual degradation rate of the PV modules, r indicates the discount rate, and N indicates the expected lifetime.

The integration costs were included in the system LCOE as annual expenditures, with the exception of the curtailment costs, which were added as indirect costs to assess the economic losses due to the curtailed energy. As in ref. [4], they were evaluated as a reduction of the nominal PV production and expressed as a percentage of PV curtailed, determined for each energy system node.

The increased penetration of VRES production on both the distribution and transmission grids resulted in increased transmission and distribution network costs, as well as adequacy expenses. They were included in the system LCOE to reflect the economic effort required to strengthen and renovate the grid

infrastructure to improve VRES production integration, hence avoiding grid instability and ensuring the security of supply. As suggested in ref. [4], the reinforcing transmission network and adequacy costs were calculated based on the investment planned by the national transmission system operator (TSO) for RES integration and quality of service and proportionally allocated between the PV and wind production for each scenario considered. It was assumed that the TSO investment was addressed to the additional PV production with respect to the current PV production as shown in Equation (2) and (3) for the scenarios without and with the flexible demand, respectively.

$$\text{Tr}_{\text{PV,noflex}} = \frac{\text{Tr}_{\text{Inv to PV},n,x} * \frac{\text{PV}_{\text{prod},n,x}}{\text{VRES}_{\text{prod},n,x}}}{\text{PV}_{\text{prod},n,x} - \text{PV}_{\text{prod},n,\text{ref}}} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Tr}_{\text{PV,flex}} = \frac{\text{Tr}_{\text{Inv to PV},n,x} * (1 - \Delta \text{cap}_{\text{opt},n,x}) * \frac{\text{PV}_{\text{prod},n,x}}{\text{VRES}_{\text{prod},n,x}}}{\text{PV}_{\text{prod},n,x} - \text{PV}_{\text{prod},n,\text{ref}}} \quad (3)$$

where Tr_{PV,noflex} and Tr_{PV,flex} are the reinforcing transmission network costs (€ MWh⁻¹) estimated for the scenarios without (noflex) and with (flex) the flexible demand activated, respectively; Tr_{Inv to PV,n,x} refers to the TSO investment for RES integration (€) associated with the PV production in the node n and

the scenario x ; $PV_{prod,n,x}$ is the PV production (MWh) in the node n and the scenario x ; $VRES_{prod,n,x}$ is the total VRES production (MWh) in the node n and the scenario x ; $PV_{prod,n,ref}$ is the PV production (MWh) in node n and reference scenario; and $\Delta cap_{opt,n,x}$ is the difference in percentage between the optimized transport capacity in the noflex and flex cases of the node n and the scenario x .

The same mathematical expressions were used to calculate the adequacy costs while taking into account the TSO investment in improving the quality of services.

Instead, the reinforcing distribution network costs were obtained from the PV Parity Project,^[13] which provided the reinforcing distribution network costs for various EU countries and were assumed to be constant across all scenarios.

The balancing costs were included to account for the effects of VRES intermittency on the existing fossil fuel power plants, which would be increasingly used to meet the peak demand rather than the baseload for which they were designed. They were drawn from the analysis presented in ref. [14], which was based on the time dependency of transient operations of fossil fuel power plants. The time-dependent constraints were the start-up costs and ramp constraints as a function of the power plant's type and shutdown hours, as well as the decay of efficiency at partial load that occurred when the power plant was operating differently from the nominal conditions, expressed in terms of additional fuel consumption and emissions. As for the case of the reinforcing distribution network costs, the balancing costs were treated the same across all scenarios.

Storage costs were defined as the additional expenses incurred in installing and managing new storage capacity to better integrate the VRES production and reduce the risk of curtailment, assuming that they are centralized and managed by the TSO itself. They are estimated based on the capacity of BESS optimized with the energy system model, as shown in Equation (4). These costs are proportionally allocated between PV and wind, assuming that the energy entering the batteries may come from either solar or wind power with equal probability.

$$Sto_{PV} = \frac{Inv_{BESS,x} * cap_{opt,n,x} * \frac{PV_{prod,n,x}}{VRES_{prod,n,x}}}{VRES_{prod,n,x}} \quad (4)$$

where $Inv_{BESS,x}$ is the BESS investment costs (€ MWh^{-1}) applied to the scenario x ; $cap_{opt,n,x}$ refers to the optimized BESS capacity (MWh) in the node n and the scenario x ; $PV_{prod,n,x}$ is the PV production (MWh) in the node n and the scenario x ; and $VRES_{prod,n,x}$ is the total VRES production (MWh) in the node n and the scenario x .

For all the scenarios, the integration costs were computed taking into account the effects of flexible demand by optimizing the BESS-installed capacity and the transmission lines transport capacity.

2.2. Energy System Model and Flexibility Assessment

As in ref. [12], the flexibility assessment was carried out using the energy system modeling tool oemof,^[15,16] which is an open-source Python tool that employs a multi-node method to dispatch power generation sources. The model's nodes were defined by

energy demand and installed capacity for each technology (including storage), and they were connected through powerlines based on the transport capacity from one node to another.

The dispatch of energy sources was performed on an hourly basis for a reference year with the aim of minimizing the system costs. Therefore, specific hourly profiles and installed capacities for each model's node defined RES technologies, whereas the fossil fuel power plants were modeled setting the installed capacity and specific efficiency. Storage systems were classified according to their type, specific nominal, charging and discharging capacities, as well as their efficiency. The demand had its own hourly profile that was provided as input for each system node.

Specific technology costs (investment and operating and maintenance costs), fuel costs and CO₂ emissions, and operational lifetime were required to accomplish the hourly dispatch of resources. The model outputted the hourly production profiles of the various power generation technologies, the hourly inflows and outflows from storage and transmission lines, and the electricity that needed to be curtailed for each system node.

In this study, the flexible demand was primarily composed of electric vehicles and heat pumps; therefore, it was determined by starting with the electricity demand of the transport sector given in ref. [17] and then applying the demand ratio of the transport and building sectors as in ref. [12]. The flexible demand was characterized by its own hourly profile, built based on,^[18,19] as shown in **Figure 1**, and was distributed among the nodes proportionally to the current distribution of the baseload or VRES, depending on the scenario considered.

By separating the hourly profile of flexible demand from the baseload, its impacts on the energy system could be more easily identified. In this study, only load shifting was applied, with load shifting intervals of 3 and 12 h, according to the intervals provided in ref. [9] for residential, industrial, and tertiary sectors.

The impacts of load shifting were evaluated using an investment-based expansion capacity optimization of BESS and powerline transport capacity applied to different scenarios, which were described in detail in Section 2.3. The optimized capacities varied only based on the activation or deactivation of the flexible demand, as all supply-side data remained constant across all scenarios considered. However, the potential costs associated with unlocking load flexibility, such as infrastructure upgrades and technology investments to enable flexibility on the consumption side, were not modeled in this study. The analysis focused on the duration of load flexibility to reduce PV integration costs, assuming that it could perfectly substitute the storage in terms of flexibility duration.

2.3. Description of the Case Study and Main Assumptions

This analysis used the Italian energy system and its expected configuration in 2030 and 2040, subdividing the national territory into six main macro regions (North, Central North, Central South, South, Sardinia, and Sicily).

The Italian energy system configuration in the 2022 was taken as reference for the distribution of capacities and load among the system's nodes. The national and regional data were provided by the Italian TSO^[20] and Gestore dei Servizi Energetici.^[21] Instead, the future scenarios were based on the European Fit-for-55

Figure 1. Comparison of the hourly profiles of a) the baseload and b) the flexible demand during a week.^[12]

(FF55)^[22] and the Green Deal goals,^[2] which were translated into various national scenarios by the Italian TSO in refs. [17,23], with the FF55 and the Distributed Energy Italia (DEIT) scenarios chosen to represent the Italian electricity system in 2030 and 2040, respectively.

The overall electricity demand was predicted to rise by 15–30% in future scenario compared to current levels, peaking at 418 TWh in the DEIT 2040 scenario. Taking into account the demand’s ratio of the transport and building sectors, the overall flexible demand available in the FF55 2030 scenario was ≈ 45.3 TWh, which corresponded to the 12.4% of the total demand, and 85.3 TWh in the DEIT 2040 scenario, equivalent to the 20.4% of the total demand. The flexible demand was then divided among the macro regions based on the current regional load distribution, as shown in **Table 1**. In the DEIT 2040 scenario, it was also assumed to be distributed proportionally to the VRES production (DEIT_b 2040 scenario).

In each of these scenarios, three sub-cases were implemented: the first was referred to as the noflex case, in which the total electrical demand was the sum of the baseload and the flexible load but load shifting was not active; the second and third sub-cases corresponded to the activation of load shifting with shift intervals of 3 and 12 h, respectively.

RES output would meet the majority of the additional demand that would arise in the future. In particular, the VRES-installed capacity was likely to grow greatly in the future Italian scenarios.

The wind capacity was predicted to increase from 12 today to 27 GW in the 2030 and 42 GW by 2040. The PV capacity would increase from 25 to 75 GW in 2030 and 114 GW in 2040, accounting for almost 70% of total VRES capacity. **Figure 2** provides a comprehensive picture of the evolution of the installed capacity of various technologies for the three scenarios examined in this analysis.

According to ref. [17], the South region would host about 50% of the wind capacity (including onshore and offshore), with the remaining 28.5% being installed in the two main islands, Sardinia and Sicily. Conversely, the majority of the distributed PV installations (around 55.8%) were expected to be found in the North region due to the abundance of roofs and other surfaces suitable for installation. Meanwhile, the majority of utility-scale PV installations (around 75.8%) were projected to be found in the sunniest regions, which included Central South, South, and the two major islands. This distribution resulted from the TSO’s requests for the connection and the exploitability of VRES depending on the location, degree of radiation, wind speed, and legal boundaries of each individual Italian region.

This large rise in VRES penetration would be accompanied by a commensurate increase in storage capacity and transmission grid infrastructure investment. The current 3 GWh of BESS capacity^[24] was predicted to increase to 94.8 GWh in 2030 and 174.8 GWh in 2040; 83% of this capacity would come from

Table 1. Baseload and flexible demand distribution among the considered macro regions for the scenarios FF55 2030 and DEIT 2040. In the scenario DEIT_a 2040, the flexible demand is distributed proportionally to the baseload, whereas it is distributed proportionally to the VRES production in the DEIT_b 2040 scenario.

TWh	FF55 2030 scenario		DEIT_a 2040 scenario		DEIT_b 2040 scenario	
	Baseload	Flexible load	Baseload	Flexible load	Baseload	Flexible load
North	184.7	26.0	191.6	49.0	191.6	19.1
Cnorth	27.5	3.9	28.5	7.3	28.5	4.6
Csouth	53.4	7.6	55.5	14.2	55.5	15.9
South	27.3	3.9	28.5	7.3	28.5	26.3
Sardinia	8.8	1.2	9.1	2.3	9.1	7.9
Sicily	19.0	2.7	19.7	5.0	19.7	11.3
Total	320.7	45.3	332.9	85.1	332.9	85.1

Figure 2. Evolution of the installed capacity of the different technologies in the year 2022 (on the left), 2030 (in the middle), and 2040 (on the right).

centralized storages, primarily found in the regions with the greatest concentration of VRES installations (South, Sardinia, and Sicily).

In comparison to the value reported in ref. [4], which pertained to the year 2019, the updated version of the TSO Development Plan reported in ref. [17] implied that investments in the grid infrastructure for RES integration and the quality and reliability increased on average by around 120 and 95%, respectively. Similar to ref. [4], the adequacy costs were determined by taking into account the expenditures made for the quality of service in conjunction with the goal of RES integration, while the reinforcing transmission network costs were determined by taking into account the investments made for only RES integration. When an intervention encompassed multiple macro regions and/or objectives, the investment was distributed equally among the macro regions and/or objectives to prevent double counting. This was because there was no precise information available regarding the allocation of funds to specific regions or objectives relative to one another. **Table 2** reports the resulting investment costs.

The PV Parity Project^[13] provided the costs of the reinforcing distribution network, which varied from €0.25 to €0.9 MWh⁻¹ for Italy. For all macro regions and scenarios in this study, the maximum value was maintained constant as a conservative estimate.

The balancing costs, which come from ref. [14], added up to €6.4 MWh⁻¹. This was the total of €4.8 MWh⁻¹ for start-up costs and €1.6 MWh⁻¹ for efficiency cost decay. For every

scenario and every macro region, the total balancing costs remained the same.

The majority of the techno-economic factors specific to generation technologies remained unchanged from refs. [4,5,12]. **Table 3** summarizes the updated PV and BESS investment costs for 2022, 2030, and 2040, as reported in refs. [25–27].

Other PV techno-economic factors, such as lifetime (30 years), discount rate (10% as a conservative assumption of utility-scale PV plants), operation and maintenance expenses (2% of the investment), and PV degradation rates (0.5%), were revised and confirmed as in refs. [28,29].

Table 2. Italian TSO investments for RES integration and quality of the service as reported in the 2023 Development Plan, which are used to estimate the reinforcing transmission network and adequacy costs, respectively.

Macro region	Investment for RES integration [M€]	Investment for quality of the service [M€]
North	649.0	149.0
Cnorth	953.2	185.9
Csouth	1934.8	476.5
South	1559.3	579.5
Sardinia	620.7	387.3
Sicily	1334.5	838.9
Total	7052.2	2617.1

Table 3. Investment costs assumption for the PV and BESS capacity in the reference 2022, FF55 2030, and DEIT 2040 scenarios.

Technology	Reference 2022 scenario	FF55 2030 scenario	DEIT 2040 scenario
PV [€ kW ⁻¹]	830	500	380
BESS [€ kWh ⁻¹]	209	117	80

3. Results

As previously stated, the system LCOE calculation includes the following integration costs: reinforcing distribution and transmission network costs, adequacy costs, balancing costs, curtailment costs, and storage costs. However, because the balancing and the reinforcing distribution network costs are constant in all scenarios analyzed, the effects of flexible demand are only evaluated in terms of savings in powerline transport capacity (reinforcing transmission network and adequacy costs), BESS (storage costs), and curtailment (curtailment costs).

Flexible demand can reduce powerline transport capacity by an average of 4% in the FF55 2030 scenario with 3 h shift interval when compared to the FF55 2030 scenario without the flexible demand activated. The highest possible decrease is around 9%, which is achieved in the Central North–Central South connection. Extending the shift interval to 12 h yields negligible benefits in terms of reduced powerline transport capacity. A similar tendency is shown in the DEIT 2040 scenarios with 12 h shift interval. However, the DEIT_b 2040 scenario achieves the biggest gain in terms of transport capacity savings, which average

Table 4. Macro regional BESS-installed capacity in the FF55 2030 scenarios optimized in this study.

GWh	FF55 2030 noflex	FF55 2030 3 h	FF55 2040 12 h
North	0	0.0	0.0
Cnorth	4.5	4.6	3.2
Csouth	13.0	10.5	5.5
South	3.4	2.6	0.6
Sardinia	5.7	5.2	3.8
Sicily	9.6	9.2	6.9
Total	36.2	32.1	20.0

Table 5. Macro regional BESS-installed capacity in the FF55 2030 scenarios optimized in this study.

GWh	DEIT_a 2040 noflex	DEIT_a 2040 3 h	DEIT_a 2040 12 h	DEIT_b 2040 noflex	DEIT_b 2040 3 h	DEIT_b 2040 12 h
North	63.7	65.2	51.8	40.5	41.1	34.8
Cnorth	25.7	25.0	19.8	19.2	20.8	17.0
Csouth	55.9	52.8	40.0	52.6	50.6	42.7
South	13.8	13.0	5.6	40.1	37.5	18.0
Sardinia	9.3	9.0	7.2	14.4	14.2	9.4
Sicily	20.0	19.5	15.3	21.9	21.9	16.0
Total	188.4	184.5	139.7	188.7	186.1	137.9

roughly 7%, because the system can use a greater amount of variable load in regions where the VRES penetration is higher. In this case, the maximum reduction in transport capacity is around 14% for the Central South–South connection.

The total PV curtailed in the FF55 2030 scenario, without the flexible demand enabled, is around 5.6 TWh. By applying the 12 h shift interval to the flexible demand profile, this can be decreased up to 5.1 TWh, or a maximum reduction of 9.1%. Instead, the influence of flexible demand on the curtailment is negligible (around 1%) in the DEIT 2040 scenarios, which is ≈4.9 TWh in the DEIT_a 2040 scenario and 5.3 TWh in the DEIT_b 2040 scenario.

The most significant impact of flexible demand is on the storage capacity requirements. In the FF55 2030 scenario, the BESS capacity is lowered by ≈11 and 45% with the 3 and 12 h shift intervals, respectively, resulting in a capacity reduction from 36.2 GWh in the FF55 2030 scenario without the flexible demand activation (FF55 2030 noflex scenario), to 32.1 and 20 GWh. Instead, the maximum gains feasible in the DEIT 2040 scenarios are roughly 25%, resulting in a drop in BESS capacity reduction from 188.4–188.7 to 137.9–139.7 GWh with 12 h shift interval, and only a slight increase to 184.5–186.1 GWh with the 3 h shift interval. When compared to the current 3 GWh installed, these results indicate that the BESS-installed capacity shall rise by at least four times during the next 15 years.

The regional trend of the BESS-installed capacity is shown in Table 4 for the FF55 2030 scenarios and in Table 5 for the DEIT 2040 scenarios.

Figure 3 displays the corresponding average, minimum, and maximum values for the storage, adequacy, and reinforcing transmission network costs obtained in each scenario.

In all the scenarios, Sardinia has the lowest reinforced transmission network costs, which vary from €2.29 to €4.39 MWh⁻¹. Rather, in every scenario that is examined, the Central South node achieves the maximum values, which range from €10 to €18.95 MWh⁻¹. Conversely, the adequacy costs are maximized in all scenarios for Sicily, ranging from €3.07 to €5.87 MWh⁻¹, and minimized for the North in all situations, ranging from €0.98 and €1.76 MWh⁻¹.

In absolute terms, the overall BESS capacity required in the DEIT 2040 scenarios is much greater than that in the FF55 2030 scenario, resulting in higher storage costs. The minimum value of €0 MWh⁻¹ is achieved for the North in the FF55 2030 scenarios, €2.91–€20.85 MWh⁻¹ for the South in the DEIT 2040 scenarios. In contrast, the maximum values are found for Central

Figure 3. Average, minimum, and maximum values of the reinforcing transmission network costs, adequacy costs, and storage costs for all the scenarios considered.

North between €50.79 MWh⁻¹ in the FF55 2030 scenario with 12 h shift interval and €185.93 MWh⁻¹ in the DEIT_a 2040 scenario without the flexible demand activation.

The total integration costs (excluding curtailment costs) range from a minimum value of €13.27 MWh⁻¹ in the FF55 2030 scenario with a 3 h shift interval and a maximum value of €207.91 MWh⁻¹ in the DEIT_a 2040 scenario without flexible demand activation. These values are obtained by adding the

constant values of €6.4 MWh⁻¹ for the balancing costs and €0.9 MWh⁻¹ for the reinforcing distribution network costs.

Figure 4 illustrates how the curtailment risk reduction affects the final system LCOE in terms of the average, minimum, and maximum values of the predicted PV generating costs, with all other integration costs set to zero.

The minimum values in all scenarios pertain to Sicily, the Italian region with the highest irradiation and with an average

Figure 4. Average, minimum, and maximum values of the PV generation costs with only the curtailment risk included for all the scenarios considered in this study.

Figure 5. Average, minimum, and maximum values of the system LCOE in all the scenarios considered.

risk of PV curtailment around 4%. Instead, the maximum values are all attributed to the South, which has the largest risk of PV curtailment, at 40% on average.

All of these impacts and associated costs are combined, and the total system LCOE is estimated, with the average, minimum, and maximum values for all scenarios evaluated presented in **Figure 5**.

The final system LCOE varies significantly across the scenarios. It is possible to see that it is higher in the DEIT 2040 scenarios due to the increased need of BESS compared to the FF55 2030 scenarios. Indeed, the storage costs account for 20–30% of the system LCOE in the FF55 2030 scenarios and 50% on average in the DEIT 2040 scenarios. This is due to the flexible load composition, which is dominated by demand for electric vehicles (75%), the majority of which are expected to consume power at night. This implies a mismatch between the flexible load demand and the PV production profile, which is worsened in the 2040 scenarios where the PV output is very high, accounting for 70% of the total VRES production.

When comparing the 2030 and 2040 scenarios, the system LCOE rises due to increased RES penetration and overall demand, resulting in higher total integration costs in 2040 compared to 2030. However, within the same scenario, comparing the noflex case with the 3 or 12 h flexibility cases, it becomes clear that the system LCOE decreases. This indicates that flexible demand is effective in reducing integration costs, even though the initial value in the 2040 noflex case is higher than in the 2030 noflex case.

The system LCOE varies from €51.9 MWh⁻¹ obtained for Sardinia in the DEIT_a 2040 scenario with 12 h shift interval to €214.1 MWh⁻¹ obtained for the Central North in the DEIT_a 2040 scenario without the activation of the flexible load. Given that the average Italian zonal price over the last 5 years has been between €120 and €130 MWh⁻¹, the system LCOE results to be equal to or lower than the average Italian zonal price in all macro regions and scenarios, with the exception of the Central North, which requires a large amount of BESS.

4. Conclusions

This study aims to assess the economic impact of flexible demand on the integration and competitiveness of a specific power production technology by incorporating these economic benefits into the calculation of production costs.

The methodology first establishes a calculation method for the integration and generation costs of utility-scale PV plants, which is based on the system LCOE, where the traditional LCOE concept is extended to include integration costs as annual expenditures, with the exception of the curtailment costs, which are added as indirect costs to assess the economic losses due to the curtailed energy. Instead, the flexibility assessment is carried out using the energy system modeling tool, oemof, to the Italian energy system and its expected configuration in 2030 and 2040.

The results highlight that flexible demand can reduce the powerline transport capacity up to 9% in the 2030 scenarios and 14% in the 2040 scenarios, whereas it allows to save up to 45 and 25% of the BESS capacity in the 2030 and 2040 scenarios, respectively, corresponding to a reduction from 36 to

20 GWh in the 2030 scenarios and from 188 to 138 GWh in the 2040 scenarios. The impacts of flexible demand on the PV curtailment are negligible in the 2040 scenarios and reach a maximum reduction of 9% in the 2030 scenarios.

The total integration costs (excluding curtailment costs) range from a minimum value of €13.27 MWh⁻¹ in the 2030 scenarios and a maximum value of €207.91 MWh⁻¹ in the 2040 scenarios without flexible demand activation. On average, flexible demand can reduce generation costs from 11% to 13% by lowering overall PV integration costs, with peaks of up to 20% in some cases.

The system LCOE varies from €51.9 MWh⁻¹ obtained for Sardinia in the DEIT_a 2040 scenario with 12 h shift interval to €214.1 MWh⁻¹ obtained for the Central North in the DEIT_a 2040 scenario without the activation of the flexible load. Given that the average Italian zonal price over the last 5 years has been between €120 and €130 MWh⁻¹, market parity has been attained in all macro regions and scenarios, with the exception of the Central North, which requires a large amount of BESS.

The findings reported in this research emphasize the need for sector coupling in future RES-based energy systems to boost overall efficiency and flexibility. Flexible demand helps keep VRES costs at an acceptable level while maintaining economic profitability. Indeed, the study demonstrates the benefits of improving system flexibility in terms of PV integration costs. However, the greatest benefits come from 12 h flexibility on the consumption side, and it needs to be further investigated how to identify the flexibility sources able to provide such a long-time shift.

However, it is important to acknowledge certain limitations of this study. The first limitation concerns the economic aspects related to flexible demand activation and deactivation. The potential costs associated with unlocking load flexibility were not explicitly modeled; therefore, these costs shall be addressed in future work to provide a more comprehensive impact assessment. The second is related to the flexible demand characteristics. It has been assumed that the primary sources of flexibility are electric vehicles and heat pumps to generate an hourly profile. However, the main goal of this article is to estimate the impact of a more flexible electrical system on the integration costs of a specific technology, rather than to characterize the flexibility sources themselves. Therefore, the focus is given on the duration of flexible demand that is more effective in reducing the need for BESS and transport line. Identifying specific sources of flexibility capable of providing that type of duration is an important point to be addressed and could be the subject of a more in-depth study focused on that topic.

Despite these limitations, the findings of this study will be valuable for future research. Indeed, they will be utilized as inputs in a recently funded European project (SUPERNOVA), which will analyze the impact of PV integration and flexibility on congestions mitigation in various energy systems.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

Elisa Veronese: conceptualization (lead); data curation (lead); formal analysis (lead); methodology (lead); software (lead); validation (lead); visualization (lead); and writing—original draft (lead). **Giampaolo Manzolini:** conceptualization (supporting); methodology (supporting); and writing—review and editing (supporting). **Grazia Barchi:** writing—review and editing (supporting). **David Moser:** conceptualization (supporting); methodology (supporting); supervision (lead); validation (supporting); and writing—review and editing (supporting).

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

energy transitions, flexible energy systems, photovoltaic integration costs, system levelized costs of electricities, utility-scale PV integrations

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